

AI-Enabled Optical Inspection of Microoptics Integration with Photonic MEMS Chips for Wideband FTIR Spectroscopy

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Photonic MEMS has been proven to be a robust optical platform for sensing applications. This requires co-integration of the MEMS and off-axis all-reflective microoptics (MO) in a system in a package (SiP) manner [1]. A Michelson interferometer on an SOI chip enabling FTIR spectroscopy has been reported for a spectral range of 1.8 μm to 6.8 μm [2]. As shown in Fig. 1 (a), the interferometer is excited by the wideband light coupled through the MO while the moving mirror of the interferometer is displaced by the MEMS actuator. The output is coupled through the MO to the photodetector that produces the interferometric signal that is Fourier transformed to get the spectrum of the light. This work considers the inspection of the macroscopic quality of the MO, its integration into the SiP and the relation with the production of the interferometric signal.

The technique combines optical inspection technique and deep learning algorithm. The work encompasses inspection setup building shown in Fig. 1 (b), data collection of optical images and interferometric signals, pipeline workflow, and model evaluation processes shown in Fig. 1 (c). An imaging setup was devised, featuring a high-quality camera with a microscopic lens, a light ring for even lighting, a spectralon located beneath the camera for colour consistency and illuminating the MEMS chip and the MO for enhanced contrast and sharpness. A dataset of 602 images was collected, divided into training and validation sets with varying alignment and microoptics (MO) quality cases. Each case was labeled as pass or fail based on the interferometric signal while the MEMS chip was excited by wideband radiation light. The workflow involved image pre-processing, orientation correction via Hough lines [3], region-of-interest (ROI) detection using YOLO [4], and alignment assessment. Data augmentation techniques are applied to improve model robustness. Grayscale pre-processing is implemented to emphasize the structural details, enabling a transfer learning model for classification. Bayesian optimization was applied to tune the deep learning model's hyperparameters. Model performance was evaluated using precision, recall, and overall accuracy across training and field testing phases. During training, precision and recall both reached 100%, while in field testing, precision was 100% and recall was 96%. These results demonstrate high accuracy, showcasing the model's reliability for practical applications.

Fig. 1. Microoptics and photonics MEMS interferometer integration for ultra-wideband operation schematic in (a) and the produced white light interferometric signal produced from the exciting black body radiation light, (b) Optical inspection setup using camera and images for pass and fail cases, and (c) the image processing flow for the deep-learning AI model and confusion matrices for training, validation and field testing exhibiting high precision and recall, especially in field testing.

References

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